

METHODS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE THROUGH THE INTERNET

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ABSTRACT

The internet as a means of teaching a foreign languages is the best way to implement many of the goals and objectives of education and upbringing. New computer technologies can be used in an ordinary classroom in urban and rural schools, in general education schools, gymnasiums, lyceums. institutes and universities. They make it possible to implement modern trends in the educational systems of many countries of the world.

In teaching, a special emphasis is placed today on the child's own activity in search, awareness and processing of new knowledge. The teacher acts as the organizer of the learning process, the leader of the amateur activities of students, providing them with the necessary help and support. Today we can already say that Internet technologies are part of the general information culture of teachers and students. The information educational space is just beginning to fill up. In order to avoid inconsistency and incompetence, it is necessary that subject teachers with many years of experience contribute to filling this information resource. Therefore, it is important for teachers to know what services and for what didactic purposes they can also use in their teaching practice using modern pedagogical technologies. First of all, it is necessary to consider the possibilities of the Internet in the process of education. The emergence of the Internet in education stimulates the desire of children to learn, expands the zone of individual activity of each student, increases the speed of supplying quality material within one lesson. All this is done through e-mail correspondence with schoolchildren from other countries, the creation and implementation of joint telecommunication projects, the opportunity to read books in the original, and participation in various competitions and Olympiads. The issue of integrating the Internet into education and, in particular, its use in teaching foreign languages is currently quite relevant. This is mainly due to the fact that when using the Internet as a means of teaching a foreign language, many goals and objectives of education and upbringing are realized in the best possible way. Based on the foregoing, is to identify the didactic possibilities of the Internet in teaching

foreign languages. The Internet as an Educational Resource Computer Telecommunications in the System of Secondary Education New computer technologies can be used in an ordinary classroom in urban and rural schools, in general education schools, gymnasiums, and lyceums. They make it possible to implement modern trends in the educational systems of many countries of the world. These are global trends in education. At the same time, so far we have limited ourselves to technologies that are used in a particular lesson, in a particular school, i.e. in the face-to-face education system. It must be said that the desire for integration in the field of education, as one of the most clearly manifested trends, dictates the need to enter a single world educational space. Hence such an interest in all countries of the world to new information technologies and, in particular, to computer telecommunications, which open a window into this world space. The history of pedagogy is rich not only in innovations in the field of methods and organizational forms of education. At different stages, parallel to the development of technical thought, there was an intensive introduction of all kinds of visual aids, technical means into the educational process. Everything was done to increase the effectiveness of the proposed innovations and the educational process as a whole. Ultimately, in pedagogy and didactics, one single goal is always pursued - the upbringing and education of the younger generation. Very few technical devices have been developed specifically for the educational process. Perhaps, in this series, only a graph projector and a language phone device for foreign language lessons can be named. All other technical means teachers borrowed from everyday life: a gramophone, a record player, a tape recorder, a TV, a video recorder, and finally a computer. These useful things were created for the arrangement of various spheres of human life. Each of them has certain properties, capabilities that determine its purpose in everyday life, culture, economy, etc. And each time, based on the intended purpose of a particular technical means, we try to highlight its inherent technical qualities that can help solve the problem of a certain areas of knowledge, culture and will be useful to everyday life. Teachers have never stood on the side of this process. The development of communication systems in the economically developed countries of the world has led to the emergence of a unique Internet network. In Uzbekistan, the choice of Internet providers is quite wide and allows you to find a job opportunity that best meets the needs and capabilities of each particular subscriber. The Internet is a global network that brings together users from various organizations, government agencies and private firms, as well as private users. The prototype of the Internet was an experimental network of the US Department of Defense. Now the Internet is spread all over the world, and more than 40 million people have already become its users. Over the past few years, there have been dramatic changes in the approach of programmers to the use of computer telecommunications (CTC). The properties and functions of the CTC are becoming much more powerful, the scope, in particular in pedagogy, is expanding dramatically. There is such a powerful direction of educational activity with the use of CTC as network publications. Almost any result obtained by students during a training project or just in a lesson can be published on the Internet in a matter of minutes. In fact, any educational activity using the means of new information technologies can now not only be considered, but actually be networked. Until the mid-1990s, the Internet was mainly used to send e-mail, that is, messages and files from one user to another. Other e-mail-based features were also available: teleconferences - the exchange of opinions.

To facilitate data on the Internet, special search services were organized - computers that allow you to find the desired document. Therefore, until 1993-94, the Internet was used mainly in the scientific field. In the region of 1993-94, the situation on the Internet changed radically, and the reason for this was the emergence and widespread introduction of a new service on the network - the World Wide Web, literally translated - the World Wide Web. The WWW is the worldwide distributed database of hypertext documents contained on the Internet. Every computer with a permanent connection to the Internet can be used as a Web server and once the famous English teacher Anthony Mullan, if the computer had not been invented as a universal technical device, it would have to be created specifically for educational purposes. That is why, speaking about new information technologies in the educational process, we need to carefully separate their didactic properties and functions. By definition, E.S. Polat, "under the didactic properties of one or another means of teaching are understood the main characteristics, features of this means that distinguish them from others, essential for didactics, both in terms of theory and practice." Thus, by analyzing the quality of teaching aids, teachers seek to determine their didactic properties, and then their functions in the educational process. When classifying the didactic properties of the Internet, we consider it reasonable to single out two main classes of properties of computer telecommunications (CTC): properties associated with their telecommunications basis, i.e. their technological capabilities; properties associated with the use of computers. However, the Internet, not only being a learning tool, provides teachers and students with ample opportunities, including when learning a foreign language. Distance Learning Another major use of the Internet is distance learning, i.e. distance learning in a situation where the learner is separated from the learner by a distance. For many years this form of education has been known in our country as part-time. The strategic goal of DL is to provide citizens with the right to receive education at any level at the place of their residence or professional activity. This goal is achieved in line with the global trend of mobile dissemination of knowledge through the exchange of educational resources. It is natural that the means of achieving such a goal should be high-tech and scientifically substantiated organizational forms that have a remote character. According to the method of obtaining educational information, they distinguish: synchronous educational systems and asynchronous ones. Synchronous systems imply simultaneous participation in the process of training sessions of the trainees and the teacher. These systems include: interactive TV, audio graphics, computer teleconferencing. Asynchronous systems do not require the simultaneous participation of students and the teacher. The student himself chooses the time and plan of classes. Such systems in distance education include courses based on printed materials, audio / video cassettes, e-mail, WWW. Mixed systems that use to place documents on it. Of course, the Internet can hardly be attributed only to teaching aids. This is an information environment in which there is also a subject-educational area that fully reflects all the possibilities of the global network, all its services. That is why it is advisable to understand the didactic properties of these services, i.e. in those characteristics that may be useful for the educational process. Now everyone understands that the Internet has colossal information capabilities and no less impressive services.

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